

Low-dose intravenous anesthesia with high-flow oxygenation in anemic patients undergoing gastrointestinal endoscopy

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Abstract

High-flow nasal oxygenation (HFNO) may improve the safety of low-dose procedural sedation in high-risk patients, but data in anemia are limited. This prospective single-center study included 166 anemic adults undergoing elective gastrointestinal endoscopy under low-dose propofol-based intravenous anesthesia with HFNO. The mean age was 70.79 ± 11.92 years, the mean hemoglobin was 99.39 ± 18.91 g/L, and 74.1% were ASA IV. Desaturation $\geq 85\%$ SpO₂ occurred in four patients (2.4%), with no episodes below 85% SpO₂. Higher body mass index (≥ 36.33 kg/m²) was associated with desaturation, whereas hemoglobin levels showed no significant relationship with hypoxemia. Regimens combining propofol with ketamine required substantially lower propofol doses (maximum 0.91 mg/kg vs. 2.94 mg/kg without ketamine; $p < 0.0001$). HFNO enabled safe low-dose propofol anesthesia in anemic patients with complex comorbidities, while ketamine coadministration provided a marked propofol-sparing effect.

Keywords

anemia, endoscopy, high-flow oxygen, propofol, sedation

Introduction

The number and complexity of gastrointestinal (GI) endoscopic procedures continue to increase, with longer procedural durations and a growing need for therapeutic interventions requiring deep sedation or general anesthesia. In an emergency hospital setting, these procedures are frequently performed under time-sensitive conditions in patients with highly variable laboratory findings, particularly those presenting with anemia, further increasing clinical and anesthetic complexity (Carron et al. 2022).

Current recommendations of the British Society of Gastroenterology and the American Society for Gastrointestinal Endoscopy emphasize appropriate patient selection, vigilant monitoring, and anesthetic expertise in complex or high-risk cases (Lin et al. 2019; Nay et al. 2021).

Propofol-based sedation remains the gold standard for GI endoscopy because of its rapid onset and recovery profile (Lin et al. 2019). However, propofol is associated with dose-dependent respiratory depression, upper airway obstruction, and hypotension (Lin et al. 2019; Nay et al. 2021). Hypoxemia is one of the most frequent and clinically significant adverse events during deep sedation for upper gastrointestinal endoscopy (Tao et al. 2022; Khanna et al. 2023). The risk is particularly elevated in vulnerable populations, including obese patients, those with obstructive sleep apnea, and patients undergoing prolonged procedures (Ng et al. 2023; Wei et al. 2024; Mohamed and Selima 2025).

Anemia represents an underrecognized risk factor in procedural sedation. Reduced hemoglobin concentration lowers arterial oxygen levels, despite preserved SpO₂, thereby diminishing oxygen delivery to tissues. In this context, even short episodes of oxygen desaturation may have greater physiological consequences. Preventing hypoxemia in anemic patients is therefore of particular importance.

High-flow nasal oxygenation (HFNO), also termed high-flow nasal cannula (HFNC) or nasal high flow (NHF), delivers heated and humidified oxygen at high flow rates with adjustable FiO₂ (concentration of inhaled oxygen). HFNO improves oxygenation by increasing the delivered FiO₂, generating mild positive airway pressure, reducing anatomical dead space, and improving CO₂ washout (Ayuse et al. 2020a). Multiple randomized studies have demonstrated that HFNO reduces hypoxemia cases compared with conventional oxygen therapy (COT) during gastrointestinal endoscopy under deep sedation. However, the magnitude of benefit remains variably reported, and evidence in specific high-risk populations, including anemic patients, remains limited (Carron et al. 2022).

Given that respiratory depression and airway obstruction during sedation are dose-dependent phenomena, re-

ducing the anesthetic dose while maintaining oxygenation may enhance safety.

It was hypothesized that the use of high-flow oxygen in anemic patients undergoing endoscopy would permit safe procedural sedation with lower doses of anesthetics without increasing oxygen desaturation cases.

The primary aim of this study was to evaluate whether HFNO reduces the incidence of hypoxia in anemic patients undergoing GI endoscopy under low-dose propofol-based intravenous sedation. Secondary aims included comparison of the total anesthetic dose, desaturation rate, and connection with BMI and hemoglobin.

Materials and methods

A prospective single-center study was conducted at University Hospital “N. I. Pirogov,” Sofia, Bulgaria, between February 2022 and February 2026, including 166 adult patients with anemia scheduled for elective gastrointestinal endoscopy under intravenous procedural sedation.

Inclusion criteria: hemoglobin below the lower reference point for gender: <130 g/L (male) or <120 g/L (female); American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I–IV.

Exclusion criteria: severe cardiopulmonary instability, requirement for endotracheal intubation, and contraindication to HFNO.

Descriptive statistics were used for demographic and medical data. Data are presented as means and standard deviations and as numbers or percentages for continuous and categorical variables. The data were processed with PSPP.

Oxygenation strategy

Oxygen was delivered using a high-flow nasal cannula system with active heated humidification (OH-70C, Micolme Medical Technology). The system was set to deliver an FiO₂ of 0.5 at a flow rate of 30 L/min, with gas heated to 37 °C and fully humidified.

Sedation protocol

Sedation was administered by an anesthesiologist using an intermittent bolus approach with propofol-based regimens. All patients received premedication with 1 mg midazolam. Depending on clinical judgment, sedation was achieved using propofol in combination with fentanyl or propofol in combination with ketamine. Drug dosing was adjusted according to patient characteristics, including age, body weight, and comorbidities.

The depth of sedation was assessed using the Ramsay Sedation Score (RSS).

Monitoring

Continuous monitoring was applied in all cases, including peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂), electrocardiography (ECG), non-invasive blood pressure, and respiratory rate. End-tidal CO₂ monitoring was used when available.

Outcomes

The primary outcome of the study was the incidence of oxygen desaturation during the procedure. Desaturation was defined as a decrease in peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂) to ≤85%, while severe hypoxemia was defined as SpO₂ <70%.

Secondary outcomes included the total propofol dose, expressed as mg/kg body weight, and its association with different sedation regimens, propofol with ketamine versus propofol without ketamine.

Additional analyses were performed to evaluate the relationship between desaturation and patient-related factors, including body mass index (BMI) and hemoglobin levels, as well as the association between hemoglobin levels and propofol dose.

Results

A total of 166 patients, including 67 (40.4%) males and 99 (59.6%) females, were observed during the period. All received intravenous sedation during elective endoscopy, with selection of propofol with midazolam, ketamine, or fentanyl. The minimum age was 36 years, and the maximum was 94 years, with a mean of 70.79 ± 11.92 years.

In 124 (74.7%) cases, both gastroscopy (FGS) and colonoscopy (FCS) were performed. In 12 subjects, only gastroscopy was performed, and in 30 cases (18.8%), only colonoscopy was performed (Table 1).

Table 1. Procedure distribution.

Procedure	Frequency	Percent
FCS	30	18.1%
FGS	12	7.2%
FGS/FCS	124	74.7%
Total	166	100.0%

Distribution by ASA is shown graphically in Fig. 1.

The mean BMI for all cases was 28.01 ± 6.56; the minimum was 17.96, and the maximum was 54.69. A graphical distribution of BMI in all cases is presented in Fig. 2.

The mean hemoglobin was 99.39 ± 18.91 g/L, the minimum was 45.0 g/L, and the maximum was 126 g/L (Fig. 3).

In the cases where ketamine with propofol was used, the minimum dose of propofol was 0.47 mg/kg, and the maximum dose of propofol was 0.91 mg/kg (Pearson chi-square $p < 0.0001$). In cases where propofol was used with

ASA

Figure 1. Distribution by ASA score.

Figure 2. Graphical distribution of BMI as a histogram.

Figure 3. Distribution of hemoglobin (g/L) as a histogram.

fentanyl or as a single medication, the minimum dose of propofol was also 0.47 mg/kg, and the maximum dose of propofol was 2.94 mg/kg (Pearson chi-square $p < 0.0001$). A total of 98 cases (59%) were performed without ket-

amine, while ketamine was used in 68 cases (41%). The dose of ketamine is shown in Table 2.

The dose of propofol as mg/kg is presented graphically in Fig. 4.

Table 2. Medication with ketamine.

Ketamine mg	Frequency	Percent
None	98	59.0%
10.00	5	3.0%
40.00	31	18.7%
50.00	32	19.3%
Total	166	100.0%

Figure 4. Propofol dose in mg/kg for all cases.

The effective dose of propofol in mg/kg used in all cases was shown to be lower in patients with lower levels of hemoglobin. Higher effective propofol doses (mg/kg) were observed in patients with higher hemoglobin levels. This result is presented graphically as a scatterplot in Fig. 5.

No signs of desaturation were observed in 162 cases (97.6%). Four cases of desaturation (2.4%) with $\geq 85\%$ SpO₂ were observed. No cases of desaturation below 85% SpO₂ were observed. Desaturation rate is presented graphically in Fig. 6.

Figure 5. Propofol dose (mg/kg) versus hemoglobin.

Desaturation

Figure 6. Desaturation rate.

Desaturation results are shown in Table 3. The significance for BMI and desaturation rate was $p < 0.0001$ for linear-by-linear association and $p < 0.067$ for Pearson chi-square. There was no significant connection between hemoglobin levels and desaturation rate: $p < 0.55$ for Pearson chi-square and $p < 0.84$ for linear-by-linear association. BMI associated with risk of desaturation was ≥ 36.33 kg/m².

Table 3. BMI and desaturation rate.

BMI	Over 85% SpO2 desaturation	Total cases
36.33	Count	1
	Total %	0.6%
42.97	Count	2
	Total %	1.2%
54.69	Count	1
	Total %	0.6%
	Count	4
	Total %	2.4%
		166
		100.0%

Discussion

This study demonstrates that the use of HFNO in anemic patients undergoing gastrointestinal endoscopy allows safe procedural sedation with a very low incidence of hypoxemia while enabling reduced-dose propofol administration. In the cohort of 166 patients, with a mean age of 70.79 ± 11.92 years and a high comorbidity burden (74.1% ASA IV), the overall desaturation rate was only 2.4%, with no episodes of severe hypoxemia. These findings are clinically significant, particularly given the high-risk profile of the studied population, characterized by advanced age, anemia (mean hemoglobin 99.39 ± 18.91 g/L), and elevated BMI (mean 28.01 ± 6.56).

Additional studies and meta-analyses have demonstrated that HFNO significantly reduces hypoxemic events during gastrointestinal endoscopy (Lin et al. 2019; Nay et al. 2021; Lee et al. 2022; Thiruvankatarajan et al. 2023).

Randomized clinical trials have confirmed these findings across different patient populations, including elderly patients undergoing sedated gastroscopy and patients undergoing more advanced endoscopic procedures under anesthesia (Mazzeffi et al. 2021; Yin et al. 2024). Importantly, the present findings extend this evidence to anemic patients, a population with reduced oxygen-carrying capacity and theoretically increased susceptibility to hypoxic injury.

Notably, no significant association was observed between hemoglobin levels and desaturation rate ($p > 0.05$), despite the expected increased risk of hypoxemia in anemic patients. This suggests that HFNO may effectively compensate for reduced oxygen reserves by maintaining consistently high FiO_2 and improving oxygen delivery at the alveolar level. In this context, HFNO may provide a physiological safety margin that mitigates the expected impact of anemia on oxygenation during procedural sedation.

An additional clinically relevant finding of this study is the significant propofol-sparing effect associated with the use of ketamine. Patients receiving the propofol–ketamine combination required substantially lower doses of propofol, with maximum doses of 0.91 mg/kg compared with 2.94 mg/kg in regimens without ketamine ($p < 0.0001$). This reduction is particularly important in elderly patients, who comprised the majority of the cohort, as propofol sedation in this population is associated with increased sensitivity and a higher risk of respiratory compromise (Heuss et al. 2003). Given that propofol-induced respiratory depression is dose-dependent, the use of ketamine as part of a multimodal sedation strategy may significantly enhance procedural safety (Ayuse et al. 2020b).

The relationship between desaturation and patient-related factors further supports the importance of respiratory mechanics over oxygen-carrying capacity in this setting. Desaturation events were significantly associated with higher BMI (linear-by-linear association; $p < 0.0001$), particularly in patients with $\text{BMI} \geq 36.33 \text{ kg/m}^2$, while no significant association was observed with hemoglobin levels. These findings are consistent with existing evidence demonstrating that obesity increases the risk of sedation-related complications through impaired respiratory mechanics, reduced functional residual capacity, and increased upper airway collapsibility (Wani et al. 2011).

From a physiological perspective, the combination of HFNO and low-dose intravenous anesthesia provides a complementary and synergistic effect. HFNO improves oxygenation through stable high FiO_2 delivery, mild positive airway pressure, and reduction of anatomical dead space. These mechanisms include washout of upper airway dead space, reduction in airway resistance, and improved respiratory mechanics (Frat et al. 2017; Renda et al. 2018; Colaianni-Alfonso et al. 2024; Liu et al. 2025). These effects may be particularly relevant in patients with impaired respiratory reserve, such as those included in the cohort.

Taken together, these findings support the use of high-flow nasal oxygen combined with low-dose, multimodal sedation as an effective and clinically applicable strategy to improve safety during gastrointestinal endoscopy. HFNO

is increasingly used in perioperative and procedural sedation settings due to its ability to enhance oxygenation and reduce hypoxemic events (Al-Husinat et al. 2023), making this approach particularly relevant for high-risk populations such as elderly and anemic patients.

In this cohort of anemic patients, HFNO maintained stable peripheral oxygen saturation, with no episodes of severe hypoxemia. The absence of a significant association between hemoglobin concentration and desaturation suggests that low-dose sedation combined with HFNO may mitigate some of the physiological vulnerability related to reduced oxygen-carrying capacity. Nevertheless, anemia remains a clinically relevant risk factor, and these findings do not support the conclusion that HFNO eliminates anemia-related risks. Further controlled studies are required to more accurately determine the specific impact of HFNO with specific anesthetic doses in this population.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. It was conducted in a single center, which may limit generalizability, and the relatively low number of desaturation events may reduce the statistical power to detect weaker associations. The observational design precludes definitive conclusions regarding causality, and sedation protocols were not fully standardized, potentially introducing variability. In addition, advanced respiratory monitoring, such as continuous capnography or arterial blood gas analysis, was not available in all cases, limiting the assessment of subtle ventilatory changes. Despite these limitations, the study provides clinically relevant real-world data in a high-risk patient population.

Conclusion

High-flow nasal oxygen therapy combined with low-dose propofol-based sedation during gastrointestinal endoscopic procedures significantly reduces hypoxemia and facilitates the use of low-dose anesthesia in anemic patients undergoing gastrointestinal endoscopy. This strategy may improve respiratory safety without compromising procedural efficacy.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

Clinical trials: Prot. EK-03-26/ 07.04.2026 Ethical committee of University Multidisciplinary Hospital for Active Treatment and Emergency Medicine “N. I. Pirogov” – Sofia, Bulgaria.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: University Multidisciplinary Hospital for Active Treatment and Emergency Medicine "N. I. Pirogov" – Sofia, Bulgaria.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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